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DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE CONCEPTS OF PHYSICAL QUALITY AND PHYSICAL ABILITY

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the differences between the concepts of physical quality and physical ability, their understanding, as well as their common and different aspects.

Key words: *Physical quality, physical ability, flexibility, strength, promptness, endurance, agility, young abilities.*

РАЗЛИЧИЯ МЕЖДУ ПОНЯТИЯМИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО КАЧЕСТВА И ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются различия между понятиями физического качества и физической способности, их понимание, а также их общие и различные аспекты.

Ключевые слова: *Физические качества, физические способности, сила, выносливость, ловкость, скорость, гибкость, возрастные способности.*

Nowadays, our esteemed President Shavkat Miromonovich pays special attention to physical culture and sports. In this regard, the Republic has raised the level of sports to the level of state policy, giving priority to the upbringing of a healthy and

harmoniously developed generation and because of the improvement and organizational foundations of any youth, sports are becoming an important factor in shaping a healthy lifestyle among students, shaping their physical and spiritual well-being.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No PF-5887 of December 4, 2019 "On measures to bring football development in Uzbekistan to a completely new level", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 30, 2021 No 261 "On measures to increase the efficiency of football clubs" and other relevant regulations in this area to ensure the quality of education serves to a certain extent in this study.

Further development of physical culture and sports in the country, involvement of all segments of the population, especially young people in regular physical culture and mass sports, ensuring transparency in the formation of the national team of Uzbekistan in sports, PF-5887 of December 4, 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to create a methodology for the selection of talented athletes and the development of football in Uzbekistan to a completely new level" and Decree No PF-5924 of January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and promote physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan". These laws and decisions serve as the main sources for the development of sports in our country

Physical training of young athletes is considered one of the most important components of sports training and is understood as a process aimed at comprehensive development of the body, strengthening of health, improvement of physical abilities and creation of a solid functional base for all other types of training.

Modern sport makes high demands on the physical fitness of the athlete. This can be explained by the following factors:

- 1) Increasing achievement in sports always requires a new level of development of physical abilities from the athlete;
- 2) A high level of physical fitness is a necessary condition for increasing training and competition loads.

In the process of forming a person's physical culture, the participants not only reduce the movements and knowledge related to them, but also develop their physical abilities.

Physical abilities are a set of psychological, physiological and morphological characteristics of a person that meet the requirements of this or that muscle activity and ensure its effective performance.

The term "physical (motor) qualities" has been used for a long time to express special aspects of human movement capabilities. Now, some authors propose to exclude it from scientific treatment due to the simple formalistic content of the concept of "physical qualities" and to leave only the term "physical abilities" in their place. Nevertheless, this term is more common in everyday speech and in scientific-methodological literature. Therefore, perhaps, it is useful to determine the similarities and differences between these two concepts, to determine the situations of their use.

First of all, it should be noted that the concept of "quality" is always used in relation to something, and it expresses its characteristic characteristic that distinguishes it from other things, in particular, a product, raw materials, food, qualities of life, of a person, the quality of knowledge and so on is spoken of in this way. In the field of physical education, this term should be used in the same sense.

Therefore, it is possible to check the physical qualities of a person in relation to one or another shape in which physical abilities are manifested, such as some characteristics of his movement capabilities, that is, to think about them based on the abilities that have been realized. A person can be the owner of various abilities that differ from each other in terms of quality. It is the silitian uniqueness of these various physical abilities that testifies to the mountain of his physical qualities. Characteristics of the quality of human abilities in life, physical education and sports are reflected in the expressions "strong", "quick", "agile", "flexibility". The importance of these qualities in life was considered as a criterion to distinguish them. In fact, physical qualities are considered the level of achievement of individual physical abilities, their accuracy, uniqueness, importance.

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